

WAYS TO ENSURE THE SAFETY OF AGRO-FOOD IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This article in agriculture, food security advantages, in theory, increase the effectiveness of the resources, important information on creating new revenue source that can get a thicker were given. Thus, the deficiencies in the current knowledge economy and the rotary toldirish I was trying to practice.*

Keywords: *households, food waste, environmental program, organic waste, greenhouse gas, and food ingredients and food loss, hydroponics.*

Introduction :

According to the united nations, the global scale of food produced at approximately 13% lost between generated and retail for approximately 17% of households in retail and the food service industry by sellers is wasted. For the budget of households not only reduce the amount of food waste, but the environment will benefit too. Less production inland, water and livestock resources means that there is less need such as this helps to reduce the benefits to the environment and agriculture and food industry waste.

United nations environmental program the scale of 931 million tons of food waste per year in the world it is estimated that approximately 74 kg every household has to make up for this.

In today's world in case of violation of the overall performance of waste households were removed 569 million tons of global food sector food service retail sales of 244 million tons and tons around 118 million, which is responsible for their waste.

In order to prevent this problem, new solutions are being developed to address the problem of food waste. The non-profit initiative, located in Geneva, provides public refrigerators and food shelves that can be used for free on the streets of the city, so cooks in all descriptions can fill them with food that they want to deteriorate. Passing people can help fruits, vegetables, bakery products and other perishable foods for free.

Refrigerators do not allow frozen items, opened food containers, prepared alcohol to maintain the health of the population, and most mines usually collect within a few hours.

Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and Uzbekistan, the Central Asian countries are faced with similar challenges such as waste management. For example, in Kazakhstan there are landfills-fat is suitable to the standard of 18%, low enough while processing solid household waste unsorted 18 percent of the population is aware of the ministry and for the reason of limited. 2017. to face the problem of waste management in Kyrgyzstan, only 30% on the collection in its territory and 10% there is a level processing. In the year 2022, according to the position in the country, more than 1.1 million tons of household waste every year 406 is formed and the ground, but only 107 of them have given permission to, as a result, there are billion tons of waste is 2.38 who occupy the area of 600 hectares. In kyrgyzstan, the practice of waste sorting is limited, first of all, None as large cities[6].

The actual ministry of the problem : food waste at the global scale, in particular, is also a pressing problem in Uzbekistan. In Uzbekistan, as in many other countries, food waste and

greenhouse gas resources as a waste of energy and environmental problems such as waste water it produces. In addition, this means lost money because of the economic importance of food for consumers and businesses sent away. Warning campaigns to fight against food waste through education and good management practices to soften the effects of this and will help ensure the stability of the food system.

Research methodology: In this article the analytical basis and created the country developed a methodological approach to the design of the waste processing parameters quotes. This approach belongs to the province of sustainable development of circular economy three tries to provide a more holistic approach, taking into the column effects. Combine the previous approaches developed for our research and analysis was established on the basis of the analytical framework. Circulating in the country has developed innovative solutions for the development of the economy.

Analysis and results.

Surprising new report published by the united nations environment program revealed the scale of the global food waste. His year's food waste by 2021 according to the index, 931 of people every year million tons of food were removed, the average of 74 kg per capita food wastecomes from. .. 569 million tons of household waste into the category, according to a report 118 of 244 million tons every year million tons of food waste while retail will be made by the service removed. UNEP which to pay the final product of the food supply chain food waste, food quality and consumer defines as good, but it still because it is broken or does not consume after the completion of the term or not. Food waste typically (but not only) in the retail and consumption stages of the food supply chain happens.

Figure-1. The distribution of food waste on the world (by sector)

Today environmental problems of the republic of Uzbekistan, in particular, great efforts has been on waste management and implementing legislative reform in this area. In April, the president of Uzbekistan for the year 2019 "for years 2019-2028 solid waste management strategy" (next to "strategy") to be received. Its purpose is to create an effective system for the processing of waste. To all companies who produce the waste reform, including that affects the life sciences industry. Uzbekistan is this new, long-term strategy to potential investors and opens great opportunities for the implementation of various projects in the field of waste management. A third of all food produced for human consumption is lost or wasted every year. In developing countries, 40 percent of food is wasted at the stage of harvesting or processing (food loss). In developed countries, consumer or retail trade (food waste) at the same stage of lose interest. In the meantime, more than three billion people ovqatlanmaydi can't buy healthy food or fed up. Can all contribute to change this situation.

These issues in Tashkent on June 30, the united nations food and agriculture organization (FAO), organized in collaboration with the ministry of agriculture of the republic of Uzbekistan " Uzbekistan on food loss and waste reduction in the formation of a strategic road map on the theme of" approved in a national seminar has been discussed.

"The adoption of a national strategy to increase the stability of the food system in Uzbekistan, as well as opens new business opportunities and will help ensure the safety of food. In addition, reducing food loss and waste products of the year 2030 in accordance with the order of the day is an important goal of the sustainable development goals. The workshop fao-turkey cooperation on food and agriculture program (FTPP II) carried out within the framework of the "central asia, reducing food loss and waste in azerbaijan and turkey" was held within the framework of the fao project. The project, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkey, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan on food loss and waste reduction measures in the development of the food system from the farmer to the consumer to help cover all of the usual network of small to take it as directed.

The main beneficiaries of the project-coaches, experts and other staff of the national institute of advanced government, non-governmental organizations and civil society organizations, as well as farmer/fisher food organizations and other value chain actors.

On April 21 the ministry of justice, " The reduction of food waste and low-income free feeding" was held, attended by the heads of the largest trade networks. Has reported the press service of the ministry about this.

In the conversation in the whole world, especially in Uzbekistan, it was noted that food waste is increasing. According to the un, around the world in the year 2019 1,64 billion tons of total food production (31 percent of food production in general) was a waste of. It should be noted that, only 25 percent of food is lost can be completely solved the problem of hunger in the world.

In Uzbekistan every year, 3 million tons of food waste is eliminated. In particular, only 2 tons of waste every day, close to 730 tons per year, the products is out of bread.

According to the analysis, the reason for the high tax burden in the country on food waste free food products food storage platform of the product the absence of problems such as the lack of food banks.

Our system will destroy the stability of our food loss and food waste. When food is wasted or lost when these food products that have been used for the production of all resources, including water, land, energy, labor, and capital-are a waste of. In addition, chiqindixonalarda food loss and waste, to destroy, waste and greenhouse gases that contribute to climate change leads to. Food loss

and waste have a negative impact food security and food will help to increase the price of food, and the existence of.

Our food system is not sustainable, durable, therefore the adoption of an integrated approach aimed at reducing food loss and waste, it is necessary to pay attention to. From the food that we produce for use at the maximum level global and local action is required. The introduction of new technologies, innovative solutions (including marketing for e-commerce platforms, mobile food products and processing systems for removable pull), food quality control and food loss and waste reduction on new work methods and best practices

.Figure 2. Distribution between livestock and farming in the maturation of agricultural products.

Agricultural products grown in the months of December 2023 January of the year of the volume of 648,6 404 billion, the sum or 2022-.compared to the corresponding period of the year 103,9 %, including farming products 679,1 202 billion. sum (104,2 %), livestock products – 969,5 201 billion, the sum of (103,7 %) make up. (2nd picture)

According to the world bank report, the global waste production by 2050 from the current level of 70% is expected to grow by. Average-income countries are expected to double in the year 2050 the production of waste, including several developing countries.

The economy of Uzbekistan and close to produces 7 million tons of solid household waste as one of only 32 percent of this amount processed. This local processing level media studies 32% by entrepreneurs for the purpose of processing the message includes the import of waste, it should be noted that open. Unfortunately, the majority of which do not meet sanitary standards axlatxonalarga the remaining waste is removed. 12 years promise of uzbekistan the production of waste reduced by 50 percent, giving get sd-2030 to achieve is faithful. However, unlike the recently held at the meeting of the parliamentary commission this stability from the target year 2030 to double production to waste worrying about come and observations were noted.

Figure-3 .In the republic, therefore, the growth of agri-food products in the years incisions.

2023 year livestock farming, hunting and services in this area, compared with the corresponding period of last year, the growth rate of 104,1 % (in 2022-.2021 respectively yanvardekabr months of the year - January-December per month than – 103,6.%), forestry – 102,7 % (in 101,7 %),fish farm – 107,4.% select (106,4 %) make up.(3-figure)

Conclusion and suggestions :

Again there is a problem that poses the restless population of the whole world. This is the problem of food waste. The severity of this problem are becoming increasingly. The storage time is prolonged through one of his solutions for plastic packaging of food products,. While oil is prepared from pet and in the production process, CO₂ is out. This contradiction in finland in 2011, carbon film packaging innovation agency, which has seen her create sponsored by processed without “Woodly” bring your's to create. "Woodly" of important events in the history of the year 2019 is the world's largest flexible packaging was the signing of the strategic cooperation agreement with one of the producers who was wipak.

Agriculture, forestry and fisheries - soil, water and air quality, biodiversity and landscape value has a significant impact. The natural ecosystem, biodiversity, sustainable practices that maintain soil fertility and water quality bio-based products is an important condition of production. It performs many vital functions of a healthy ecosystem and will provide important services to life on earth. Food, fiber and fuel in addition to provide you with a healthy ecosystem, clean air and oxygen in the form of, regulates the flow of water of the flood, which prevents it regulates global temperature and biodiversity and species and genes related to cycle the tank for feed means for make up. Performs the function of healthy soil and the oceans and the global carbon deposition plays an important role in slowing climate change and its potential effects.

We will achieve a reduction of CO₂ emissions by 1.6 million tons if food waste biofuel is used on cars moving on gasoline and diesel fuel in Uzbekistan. In the automotive industry, the durability of the material is an important parameter when choosing a design. For example, the automotive company Ford has a research program aimed at testing and applying biomaterials for various automotive applications. Some examples under study are soy-based pouliretan foam for car seats, wheat straw as structural filler for injection molding plastics, and polylactic acid or polylactide as bio-based resin for interiors. The results show that the biodegradation rate of polylactide is too high for current product requirements, but polypropylene filled with wheat straw can be successfully used in automotive interiors by eliminating 13 tons of CO₂ emissions per year.

Rural property the value of waste in our economy increases if bioactive, valuable substances such as essential oils and cartinoids, which can be extracted from waste generated in rural society, are extracted in their pure form. In agriculture, more than half of the dry mass collected worldwide consists of agricultural residues and inedible biomass such as grain and legumes; tuber, oil and sugar buds; stems, leaves and buds of vegetable crops; and pruning and garbage of fruit and nut trees. It is estimated that 121 million tons of agricultural crop residues (mostly salmon), 46 million tons of forest residues and 31 million tons of grass may be produced annually in Europe.

Development of new packaging material fibers based on tomato fibers in Uzbekistan. This innovation remains in many countries of Europe-for example, Solidus Solutions (Netherlands) has developed a new packaging material based on tomato fibers. The leaf and stem of tomato osimli, left over from Orim-YIG, are ground and mixed with processed goose fibers to produce a type of cardboard for packaging. This packaging is used by some tomato producers, including Pure Hothouse Foods of Canada and Idyl of France (Solidus Solutions, 2017).

In 2013, South Korea's food industry introduced VBFS. These measures led to a significant 50 percent reduction in waste production and a 95 percent increase in recycling rates, making South Korea a world leader in waste management and recycling.

In conclusion, it can be said that in order to improve the existing technological processes in our country and go through a fundamentally new path of development, it is necessary to comply with certain requirements, that is, reduce the production processes to the minimum number of stages, since each of them produces waste and simply loses raw materials. Policy interventions should aim to reduce environmental pressure and promote bioeconomics throughout the value chain. It requires the recognition of mutual agreements on sustainability and the development of consistent measures aimed at manufacturers and consumers and their implementation in practice. Through the effective organization of Science and production integration, scientific research is carried out by scientists and specialists of research institutes of higher educational institutions on the technology of waste-free production and its organization, and positive results are obtained.

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